

Fostering OSM's Micromapping Through Combined Use of Artificial Intelligence and Street-View Imagery

Kauê Vestena^{1*}, Silvana Camboim¹ and Daniel Santos²

¹ Department of Geomatics, Federal University of Paraná, Curitiba, Brazil; kauemv2@gmail.com, silvanacamboim@gmail.com

² Cartographic Engineering Sector, Military Engineering Institute, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; daniel.rodriques@ime.eb.br

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

This abstract was accepted to the OSM Science 2023 Conference after peer-review.

Map scale is fundamental to cartography. The International Cartographic Association's definition of a map [1] already explicitly emphasizes the selection of specific features, pointing to the process of cartographic generalization. This operation simplifies the representation of geographic data to produce a map at a given scale [2]. In the past, geospatial data was collected in a standardized way. Representations at larger scales could then be derived. However, OpenStreetMap (OSM) has changed this approach. Each object can be captured individually, resulting in digital representations of varying and distinct accuracies. Nevertheless, products such as OSM's Slippy Map Tiles are designed for consistent scales, maintaining a uniform scale for each tile. This characteristic gives users a seemingly seamless view of the map. The tile layers on the OpenStreetMap website range in maximum scale from around 1:2000 to 1:250 [3,4], suitable for mapping urban detail. In the context of collaborative mapping, the term Micromapping was coined as the "mapping of small geographic objects" [5] and appears as a topic of growing interest among the OpenStreetMap and general Volunteered Geographic Information community [5,6,7,8], can be helpful in many applications like mapping large-scale infrastructure [5]; pedestrian security and flow prediction [6]; detailed 3D model generation and indoor mapping [7]; assistive technologies like tactile maps generation [8]; and also general-purpose micro mapping rendering [9]. There is also some discussion among the OSM community about their idiosyncrasies, comprising issues that may arise when there is a bigger density of features [10]. However, it is important to remember that omitting some elements at smaller scales can improve the readability of the map. On the other hand, many street-level editors, such as MapComplete [11] emerged, bringing micro-mapping with a central role.

As of August 2023, a tiny share of mapped features can still be categorized as micromapping. According to Taginfo [12], while there are almost 572 million buildings and more than 221 million roads, the most common micromapping objects are 22 million natural=tree nodes, 12 million power=pole nodes, and 8 million highway=crossing nodes.

Vestena, K., Camboim, S., & Santos, D. (2023). Fostering OSM's Micromapping Through Combined Use of Artificial Intelligence and Street-View Imagery

In: Minghini, M., Li, H., Grinberger, A.Y., Liu, P., Yeboah, G., Juhász, L., Coetzee, S., Mooney, P., Sarretta, A., & Anderson, J. (Eds.). Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023, Antwerp, Belgium, 10-12 November 2023. Available at

<https://zenodo.org/communities/osmscience-2023>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10443310](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10443310)

© 2023 by the authors. Available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)) license.

Other important and very common urban features are also relatively ill-represented, e.g. 1.2 million benches, 1.8 million fire hydrants, and 1.2 million traffic signals. In these 3 cases, all features tend to be concentrated in Europe and the US. The literature also points out that OSM is not accumulating many contributors outside major urban areas, resulting in less dense data in those scenarios [13].

In spite of this, there is a need for quicker methods to generate data belonging to this category, which can contain objects such as those mentioned before but also properties like the width of sidewalk lanes and the presence of access ramps. Among the data freely available for extracting features for OSM, georeferenced street view imagery is one of the most valuable assets, highlighting Mapillary and KartaView platforms [14]. Terrestrial images possess a wealth of visual data that can be transformed into geospatial information. This informal description aligns with the well-established scientific discipline of photogrammetry, which has employed traditional methods like triangulation since the 19th century in conjunction with the advent of photography. These techniques have enabled the mapping of entire cities [15] and the precise capture of 3D points through multiple views [16]. Nevertheless, traditional photogrammetric procedures rely on good triangle geometry, which can be tricky considering terrestrial exposures [17] and depends on good correspondences that can fail or be challenging to achieve on surfaces without texture [18].

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a paradigm shift, introducing novel methods that deliver unparalleled performance in areas such as general automation and predictive analysis powered by big data [19]. In the present work, we are concerned with two tasks with massive recent improvements due to AI's use: Semantic segmentation [20,21,22], which is the capability to segment meaningfully digital images, giving a label for each pixel, and Monocular Depth [23,24,25] which enables to calculate 3D coordinates for any pixel. We propose combining them to harness AI's potential to speed up data generation for OSM. The proposed methodology will use street-view imagery (SVI) and metadata as primary input.

We chose the SAM - Segment Anything Model [26] and Paddleseg [27], both available under the OSM-friendly Apache-2.0 Licence, for the semantic segmentation task. We applied the MIT-Licensed ZoeDepth model [28] for Monocular Depth. The fusion process works as follows: the user selects an image whose depth map is created using ZoeDepth, then prompts for a category like "pole" or "bench", and a list of matching segments (2D pixel patches) is returned by the Paddleseg using SAM backend; then the same image regions are clipped from the depth image. In the next step, through the pixel-wise use of the projective equations alongside the known depth, 3D coloured patches are generated.

The second part is to translate those 3D patches into OSM data. This work comprises many possible features, but we will explain through an example of a street light. From the detection, we extract the base tag "highway=street_lamp". From the 3D patch, we pick the lowest point to create the geometry (latitude and longitude), the absolute elevation of the point on the ground for the tag "ele:wgs84=*" and its difference with the highest point to provide the "height=*" tag. Then, from both 2D and 3D data, other tags can be inferred, such as support=*, lamp_mount=*, light:direction=* and so on. For each category, a different set of steps shall be taken alongside the inferable tags for additional characteristics. Some patches shall provide only additional information, e.g. width=* and incline:transversal=* in the example of already-existent sidewalks mapped as separate geometries.

Up to the present, the methodology has already been tested only to the point of the 3D patch generation with a single test of the extraction of the slope of a ramp that was

measured in the cloud (angle between the normals of ramp and street-section least-squared fitted planes) as 9.13° against a smartphone-made field measurement of 9° . The forthcoming months shall follow with tests regarding the obtainable accuracy and possible improvements like the use of track-anything [29] that expand SAM to the capability of tracking the same object among many frames, enabling redundancy and thus uncertainty estimation. Another topic of concern will be how to properly fuse this data with OSM, considering that both data sources may have inconsistent spatial references.

Figure 1. The Workflow Shown Through the example of a Ramp

References

- [1] International Cartographic Association (2023). *Mission*. <https://icaci.org/mission>
- [2] Ruas, A. (2008). Map Generalization. In S. Shekhar & H. Xiong (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of GIS* (pp. 631–632). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-35973-1_743
- [3] Touya, G., & Reimer, A. (2015). Inferring the Scale of OpenStreetMap Features. In *Lecture Notes in Geoinformation and Cartography* (pp. 81–99). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14280-7_5
- [4] OSM Contributors (2023). *Zoom levels*. https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Zoom_levels
- [5] Schmid, F., Cai, C., & Frommberger, L. (2012). A new micro-mapping method for rapid VGI-ing of small geographic features. *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Geographic Information Science, USA*, 18–21.
- [6] Cohen, A., & Dalyot, S. (2019). Pedestrian Traffic flow prediction based on ANN model and OSM data. *Proceedings of the International Cartographic Association*, 2(20).
- [7] Goetz, M. (2013). Towards generating highly detailed 3D CityGML models from OpenStreetMap. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 27(5), 845–865.
- [8] Fillières-Riveau, G., Favreau, J. M., Barra, V., & Touya, G. (2020). Génération de cartes tactiles photoréalistes pour personnes déficientes visuelles par apprentissage profond. *Revue Internationale de Géomatique*, 30(1-2), 105–126.
- [9] OSM Contributors. (2023). *Straßenraumkarte Neukölln*. OpenStreetMap Wiki. https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Stra%C3%9Fenraumkarte_Neuk%C3%B6lln
- [10] OSM Contributors (2023). *Micromapping*. <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Micromapping>

- [11] MapComplete (2022). *MapComplete - editable, thematic maps with OpenStreetMap*. <https://mapcomplete.osm.be>
- [12] OSM contributors (2023). *Taginfo*. <https://taginfo.openstreetmap.org>
- [13] Quinn, S. (2015). Using small cities to understand the crowd behind OpenStreetMap. *GeoJournal*, 82(3), 455–473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-015-9695-6>
- [14] Alvarez Leon, L. F., & Quinn, S. (2018). The value of crowdsourced street-level imagery: examining the shifting property regimes of OpenStreetCam and Mapillary. *GeoJournal*, 84(2), 395–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-018-9865-4>
- [15] Grimm, A. (2007). New Products and Services from IGI. In D. Fritsch (Ed.), *Photogrammetric Week 2007* (pp. 1-10). Wichmann Verlag. <https://phowo.ifp.uni-stuttgart.de/publications/phowo07/080Grimm.pdf>
- [16] Luhmann, T., Robson, S., Kyle, S., & Harley, I. A. (2007). *Close Range Photogrammetry: Principles, Techniques, and Applications*. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:107005019>
- [17] Hartley, R., & Zisserman, A. (2003). *Multiple view geometry in computer vision*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511811685>
- [18] Chen, Y.-S., & Chen, B.-T. (2002). A solution of correspondence problem for measuring 3D surface. *2002 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, 4, IV-3553-IV-3556. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICASSP.2002.5745422>
- [19] Lu, M. (2023). The industrial revolution brought by AI: Opening the Gateway to the Future. *Geographical Research Bulletin*, 0(2), 166–168. https://doi.org/10.50908/grb.2.0_166
- [20] Guo, Y., Liu, Y., Georgiou, T., & Lew, M. S. (2018). A review of semantic segmentation using deep neural networks. *International journal of multimedia information retrieval*, 7, 87-93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13735-017-0141-z>
- [21] Hao, S., Zhou, Y., & Guo, Y. (2020). A Brief Survey on Semantic Segmentation with Deep Learning. *Neurocomputing*, 406, 302–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2019.11.118>
- [22] Wang, P., Chen, P., Yuan, Y., Liu, D., Huang, Z., Hou, X., & Cottrell, G. (2018). Understanding Convolution for Semantic Segmentation. In *2018 IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)*. 2018 IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/wacv.2018.00163>
- [23] Zhao, C., Sun, Q., Zhang, C., Tang, Y., & Qian, F. (2020). Monocular depth estimation based on deep learning: An overview. *Science China Technological Sciences*, 63(9), 1612–1627. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11431-020-1582-8>
- [24] Ming, Y., Meng, X., Fan, C., & Yu, H. (2021). Deep learning for monocular depth estimation: A review. *Neurocomputing*, 438, 14–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2020.12.089>
- [25] Bhoi, A. (2019). *Monocular Depth Estimation: A Survey*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1901.09402>
- [26] Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., Mao, H., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., Xiao, T., Whitehead, S., Berg, A. C., Lo, W.-Y., Dollár, P., & Girshick, R. (2023). *Segment Anything (Version 1)*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.02643>
- [27] Liu, Y., Chu, L., Chen, G., Wu, Z., Chen, Z., Lai, B., & Hao, Y. (2021). *PaddleSeg: A High-Efficient Development Toolkit for Image Segmentation (Version 1)*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2101.06175>
- [28] Bhat, S. F., Birkel, R., Wofk, D., Wonka, P., & Müller, M. (2023). *ZoeDepth: Zero-shot Transfer by Combining Relative and Metric Depth (Version 1)*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2302.12288>
- [29] Yang, J., Gao, M., Li, Z., Gao, S., Wang, F., & Zheng, F. (2023). *Track Anything: Segment Anything Meets Videos (Version 2)*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.11968>